

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D1.1

Project management and quality control plan

(Version 2.0, 31/05/2021)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

Deliverable:	D1.1 Project management and quality control plan	
Work Package:	WP1	
Due Date:	31/05/2021	
Submission Date:	31/05/2021	
Lead Beneficiary:	ENoLL	
Version:	2.0	
Status:	Submitted	
Author name(s):	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL), Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	
Contributor(s):		
Reviewer(s):	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Ilias Trochidis (VILABS)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Project Coordinator	
Keywords:	Project management, quality control	
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	25/04/2021	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)	ToC sent
0.2	03/05/2021	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)	First draft
0.3	27/05/2021	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Review of the document with some requests of changes
0.4	28/05/2021	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)	Changes implemented as requested by the reviewer
0.5	30/05/2021	Ilias Trochidis (VILABS)	Review of the document with some requests for changes
2.0	31/05/2021	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	Ethical Board members were added
3.0	31/05/2021	ENoLL	Sent to the EC

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
ABSTRACT	9
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	9
1.2 DESCRIPTION OF WP1 MANAGEMENT	10
2 PROJECT HANDBOOK	11
2.1 PROJECT WORKPLAN	11
2.2 WORK PACKAGES	13
2.3 PLANNED MILESTONES	14
2.4 PLANNED DELIVERABLES	14
2.5 EFFORT PER WORK PACKAGE	17
2.6 GENERAL PROVISIONS ON ELIGIBILITY OF ACTIVITIES	18
2.6.1 <i>Eligible Activities</i>	18
2.6.2 <i>Eligible Costs</i>	18
3 PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE	19
3.1 CONSORTIUM.....	19
3.2 ROLES AND ENTITIES	21
3.3 STRUCTURE.....	25
3.4 METHODOLOGY.....	26
3.4.1 <i>Online meetings' tool and file sharing</i>	27
3.4.2 <i>E-mail communication</i>	27
3.5 PROJECT MEETINGS	27
3.5.1 <i>Consortium Plenary Meetings</i>	28
3.5.2 <i>Project Steering Board meetings</i>	28
3.5.3 <i>Technical or WP meetings</i>	28
3.5.4 <i>WP leaders teleconferencing</i>	28
3.5.5 <i>WP teleconferencing</i>	28
3.6 PROJECT WEBSITE	28
4 DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT	29
4.1 CLASSIFICATION OF DOCUMENTS	29
4.2 DOCUMENT STANDARDS	29
4.2.1 <i>Allowed document types</i>	29
4.2.2 <i>Format and style guidelines</i>	29
4.2.3 <i>Compliance with Data Protection Guidelines</i>	30
4.3 VERSIONING	30
4.4 TEMPLATES	30
4.5 OTHER DOCUMENTS	31
4.5.1 <i>Publications</i>	31
4.5.2 <i>Reports and presentation</i>	31
5 PROJECT REPORTING AND FINANCING	32
5.1 GENERAL PROCEDURES AND RULES FOR PROJECT REPORTING	32
5.1.1 <i>Reporting Periods</i>	32
5.1.2 <i>Reporting process</i>	32
5.1.3 <i>Financial Report Template</i>	33
5.1.4 <i>Effort Report Template</i>	34
5.1.5 <i>Currency</i>	34

6	QUALITY ASSESSMENT	35
6.1	QUALITY EXPECTATIONS	35
6.2	QUALITY RESPONSIBILITIES OF CONSORTIUM MEMBERS	35
6.3	QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CONTROL PROCESS	36
6.3.1	<i>Quality assurance for Deliverables</i>	36
6.3.2	<i>Quality control of deliverables</i>	36
6.3.3	<i>Quality control of project management</i>	38
6.4	CONTROL OF CHANGES	38
6.4.1	<i>Technical changes</i>	38
6.5	RISK MANAGEMENT	38
6.5.1	<i>Risk identification and analysis</i>	38
6.5.2	<i>Risk monitoring and control</i>	41
7	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHT ISSUES	41
7.1	BACKGROUND	42
7.2	MONITORING OF USAGE	42
7.3	TRANSFER OF RESULTS	42
7.4	DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS	42
7.5	JOINT OWNERSHIP	43
8	REFERENCES	44

List of Figures

FIGURE 1	VITALISE GANTT CHART	12
FIGURE 2	CONSORTIUM PARTNERS ACROSS THE WORLD	19
FIGURE 3	VITALISE MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE	26
FIGURE 4	FINANCIAL REPORT TEMPLATE	33
FIGURE 5	EFFORT REPORT TEMPLATE EXAMPLE	34

List of Tables

TABLE 1	VITALISE WORK PACKAGES	13
TABLE 2	VITALISE MILESTONES	14
TABLE 3	VITALISE DELIVERABLES	17
TABLE 4	VITALISE PARTNERS' EFFORT PER WORK PACKAGE	18
TABLE 5	VITALISE PARTNERS' CONTACT DETAILS	21
TABLE 6	VITALISE WORK PACKAGE LEADERS	23
TABLE 7	VITALISE PROJECT STEERING BOARD	25
TABLE 8	VITALISE DELIVERABLES' SUBMISSION PROCEDURE	37
TABLE 9	VITALISE RISKS' IDENTIFICATION AND MEASURES	41

Abbreviations

AA	Administrative Assistant
AB	Advisory Board
AB	Advisory Board
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential, only for members of consortium (including the Commission Services)
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Ethical Board
EC	European Community
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IPA	Intellectual Property Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Properties Right
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
P	Public
PC	Project Coordinator
PL	Pilot Leader
PSB	Project Steering Board
R	Report
QRM	Quality and Risk Manager
RTD	Research and Technological Development
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The goal of this deliverable is to illustrate the project management framework of the VITALISE project along with all project quality control and operational procedures and associated roles required by the different managerial and operational activities planned for the whole project duration. This document is designed as a set of practical guidelines to help clearly define workflows and rules that the partners will have to follow throughout the project's activities, to ensure the highest quality standards are met and to strengthen project management (e.g., partner responsibilities, quality control mechanisms, documentation control, documentation formats and exchange rules).

The document lists the procedures required for a well-organised execution of the project, aiming to maximise cooperation of partners and to clearly define responsibilities among the beneficiaries of the project. Furthermore, the document clearly specifies the quality, administrative and communication procedures to be followed by the partners during the implementation of the project, to ensure full control of its development, from both a financial and a technical standpoint.

This report complements the provisions of the Grant Agreement and its annexes as well as the Consortium Agreement, which has been already signed by all the beneficiaries, in that it clearly defines several practical guidelines and rules essential for the day-to-day management of the project.

Abstract

This document reports on the management structure of the VITALISE Project, quality control procedures and ways to overcome potential barriers and risks that can be encountered during the project activities. The document also serves as the project management framework for all the partners, thus including responsible partners for each WP, their contacts and activities to be developed (both in terms of deliverables and milestones).

1 Introduction

The main goal of project management within the VITALISE project is to ensure the successful collaboration and involvement of all parties, both within the project, as well as of parties identified as part of the stakeholder ecosystem to develop, evaluate and develop the VITALISE outcomes for exploitation.

This implies that partners and central management should be continuously aware of the relationship between their own work and the work done by others. At the same time, the management has to fulfil the administrative requirements deriving from the partners' contractual relationship with the EC and implement quality control procedures that will ensure excellent outputs of the project activities, thorough quality review of the project deliverables and regular assessment of VITALISE progress and achievements. The project's management structure/procedures and quality control/internal assessment procedures are designed to achieve these goals.

Daily project management and administration beyond scientific research generally includes all non – scientific project activities, such as documentation, reporting, financial monitoring, organization of meetings and workshops, set-up of a communication structure, creation and maintenance of the project website, knowledge and IPR management within the consortium etc. The basic idea is to relieve researchers and developers from administrative chores, thereby allowing them to focus more on research and technological development (RTD) activities, resulting in more effective project work. Both scientific and administrative project activities are complementary. They are closely linked and integrated with one another, making project communication essential. On top and complementary to them, quality assurance procedures regularly assess project outcomes and guarantee their excellent quality.

Although, the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) has initial experience in coordinating European RTD and national projects, it has strong experience and track record in participation in European RTD that assists to ensure the ability of the VITALISE project to rapidly start-up and maintain professional management of financial and reporting requirements from the European Commission (EC).

Thus, this management and quality assessment plan provides a detailed description of management structures and procedures that guides day-to-day tasks and improves the project's communication effectiveness. It represents a combination of detailed procedures, templates and interactive elements. It is therefore important that all partners agree to the implementation of this Management and Quality Assessment Plan to ensure its effectiveness.

The structure of the present deliverable is as follows: Chapter 2 presents the project handbook, which gathers information on the project workplan, including timelines, lists of work packages, milestones and deliverables, as well as, the general provisions on eligibility of activities including eligibility of costs and financial management. Chapter 3 presents the management structure of VITALISE as described in the DoA and specified by partners during the kick-off meeting of the project. In Chapter 4 the Document management is discussed while general provisions for progress and financial reporting are described in Chapter 5. Chapters 6 and 7 present the Quality control plan and the main aspects of ownership and intellectual property rights.

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions

and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling inperson Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP1 Management

The main objective of this Work Package is:

- To address project objectives, meet contractual obligations and deadlines through allocation and coordination of human and financial resources.
- To represent the project to EC, report progress and ensure seamless communication interface between EC and the consortium.
- To coordinate communications between all stakeholders including partners, external experts and advisors, researchers and evaluators to ensure efficient, transparent resolution of any issues.
- To ensure compliance with legal, ethical and privacy concerns with respect to data management, identification of any personal data usage or ethical considerations and application of appropriate national or EU regulations.
- To establish and run decision-making structures and technical support to ensure goal setting, progress tracking, document management and effective information exchange.

2 Project Handbook

2.1 Project Workplan

The activities, as detailed in Table 10 of the GA, have been scheduled according to the Gantt chart, which is displayed below for convenience. VITALISE aims to enable effective and convenient access to key European research infrastructures, governed by Living Labs. This will enhance the knowledge and quality of research for European researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain. That is why the WP8, WP9, WP10 and WP12 which are the WPs for managing Transnational and Virtual Access to research infrastructures have a central role in the VITALISE work plan. WP2 and WP3 include work to be done regarding the Harmonization of procedures and the development of ICT tools to support Transnational and Virtual Access. WP4 is used as a means to better prepare researchers and enlarge the community and have the primary goal to enhance the support provided to research community. WP11 serves as a mean to identify the projects that will add value to European Research Area. WP5, WP6, WP7 are the Joint Research Activities performed within the consortium partners that will improve, in quality and quantity, the integrated services provided by the Research infrastructures and act as a “testing-bed” for the Harmonization outputs. WP1 and WP13 are the Management and Dissemination, Exploitation WPs that will run across the project to assure the overall quality of implementation and openness to European society and Research Community.

2.2 Work Packages

VITALISE is articulated in the following 13 Work Packages, whose coordinating partners are detailed in the following table.

WP	Work Package Title	WP Leader	Start month	End Month
WP1	Management	ENoLL	1	36
WP2	NA1-Common standards, Procedures and Practises	ENoLL	1	36
WP3	NA2- Implementation, improvement and optimized use of the H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools	VICOM	2	36
WP4	NA3 - Capacity Building and Training	ENoLL	4	36
WP5	JRA1 - Rehabilitation supported by technology	LICALAB	2	36
WP6	JRA2 – Transitional care	AUTH	2	36
WP7	JRA3- Everyday living environments	LAUREA	2	36
WP8	TA1 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for rehabilitation	GAIA	18	36
WP9	TA2 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care	AUTH	18	36
WP10	TA3 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living	INTRAS	18	36
WP11	NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection	SIT	6	32
WP12	VA1-Virtual Access to datasets	UPM	25	36
WP13	Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability	VILABS	1	36

Table 1 VITALISE Work Packages

2.3 Planned Milestones

The following milestones have been identified within the project.

Milestone number	Milestone name	WP number	Delivery date
MS1	Establishment of management boards	WP1	12
MS2	Standard Version 1	WP2	6
MS3	First Release of H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools	WP3	12
MS4	Final Release of H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools	WP3	36
MS5	Summer school implementation	WP4	28
MS6	Implementation postgraduate course	WP4	36
MS7	First version of evaluation procedure	WP11	12
MS8	Application for RAI patent	WP13	30

Table 2 VITALISE Milestones

2.4 Planned Deliverables

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP number	Type	Diss. level	Delivery date
D1.1	Project management and quality control plan	1	R	PU	M2
D1.2	First version of Ethics and Safety Manual	1	R	PU	M6
D1.3	Final version of Ethics and Safety Manual	1	R	PU	M24
D1.4	Data management plan (first version)	1	R	PU	M6
D1.5	Data management plan (final version)	1	R	PU	M30
D1.6	Innovation strategy (first version)	1	R	CO	M12
D1.7	Innovation strategy (final version)	1	R	CO	M24
D1.8	Management Handbook	1	R	CO	M3
D2.1	Standard Version 1	2	R	PU	M6
D2.2	Evaluation process and tools	2	R	PU	M12

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP number	Type	Diss. level	Delivery date
D2.3	Standard Version 2	2	R	PU	M12
D2.4	Standard Version 3	2	R	PU	M18
D2.5	Standard Version 4	2	R	PU	M24
D2.6	Standard Version 5	2	R	PU	M30
D2.7	Standard Version 6	2	R	PU	M36
D2.8	First version of user requirements	2	R	PU	M10
D2.9	Final version of user requirements	2	R	PU	M24
D3.1	VITALISE Service specification	3	R	PU	M18
D3.2	RAI Service specification	3	R	CO	M20
D3.3	Anonymisation and Synthetic data algorithm	3	R	PU	M28
D3.4	Panel Management Tool	3	DEM	PU	M16
D3.5	VITALIZE SDK Manual	3	OTHER	PU	M18
D3.6	Certified Node OS installation image	3	OTHER	PU	M16
D4.1	Online educational material (first version)	4	OTHER	PU	M18
D4.2	Online educational material (final version)	4	OTHER	PU	M36
D4.3	Printed educational material (first version)	4	OTHER	PU	M18
D4.4	Printed educational material (final version)	4	OTHER	PU	M36
D4.5	Living Lab Guidelines (first version)	4	R	PU	M24
D4.6	Living Lab Guidelines (final version)	4	R	PU	M36
D4.7	University Course design	4	R	PU	M18
D4.8	Boosting commercialisation potential of research results	4	R	PU	M12
D5.1	Submission of research protocol in peer reviewed journal	5	R	CO	M6

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP number	Type	Diss. level	Delivery date
D5.2	Ethical application documents	5	R	PU	M12
D5.3	Summary and results of the performed activities	5	R	PU	M36
D6.1	Submission of research protocol in peer reviewed journal	6	R	CO	M6
D6.2	Ethical application documents	6	R	PU	M12
D6.3	Summary and results of the performed activities	6	R	PU	M36
D7.1	Submission of research protocol in peer reviewed journal	7	R	CO	M6
D7.2	Ethical application documents	7	R	PU	M12
D7.3	Summary and results of the performed activities	7	R	PU	M36
D8.1	First interim report on Transnational Access	8	R	PU	M28
D8.2	Final report on Transnational Access	9	R	PU	M36
D9.1	First interim report on Transnational Access	9	R	PU	M28
D9.2	Final report on Transnational Access	9	R	PU	M36
D10.1	First interim report on Transnational Access	10	R	PU	M28
D10.2	Final report on Transnational Access	10	R	PU	M36
D11.1	Material for open calls	11	OTHER	PU	M30
D11.2	Application toolkit	11	OTHER	PU	M30
D11.3	Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals	11	R	PU	M32
D12.1	Final interim report on Virtual Access	12	R	PU	M36
D12.2	Report from VITALISE platform access and usage	12	R	PU	M36
D13.1	Dissemination and Communication plan	13	R	PU	M3

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP number	Type	Diss. level	Delivery date
D13.2	Dissemination and Communication activities report	13	R	PU	M18
D13.3	Innovation Management report	13	R	CO	M18
D13.4	Exploitation, Sustainability and Business plan	13	R	CO	M18
D13.5	Dissemination and Communication activities report	13	R	PU	M36
D13.6	Exploitation, Sustainability and Business plan	13	R	CO	M36
D14.1	H - Requirement No. 1	14	Ethics	CO	M8
D14.2	POPD – Requirement No. 3	14	Ethics	CO	M8
D14.3	GEN – Requirement No. 4	14	Ethics	CO	M12

Table 3 VITALISE Deliverables

2.5 Effort per Work Package

Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	WP10	WP11	WP12	WP13
ENoLL	18	14	3.5	17	3	3	3	0	0	0	4	0	8.5
AUTH	8	5.5	12.5	4	5.5	9	3	4.40	4.70	4.70	0.5	0.9	3.5
LAUREA	1.5	4.5	0.5	4	2	2	8.5	3.30	0	0	2	0.6	2
LICALAB	1.5	3	0.5	4	8	2	2	4.10	2.80	3.30	1.5	0.9	1.5
INTRAS	1.5	2	0.5	2	2	2	4.5	4.30	4.30	4.30	1	0.9	1.5
TREBAG	1.5	3.5	1.5	6	2	2	6	0	0	4.10	1.5	0.3	3
GAIA	1	2	0.5	3	5	0	1.5	3.50	0	3.50	0	0.6	1.5
VICOM	1.5	1	33	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.5	0	4
CERTH	1.5	1	22	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	3
AIT	1.5	3	0.5	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	4	0	0.3	1.5
SIT	4	3.5	5.5	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	3

Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	WP10	WP11	WP12	WP13
UPM	3	3	0.5	4	3	3	3	7.80	3.90	0	0	0.3	1.5
WITA	1	1	16.5	2	1.5	1.5	1.5	0	0	0	0	0	2
AV	2	1	2	6.5	2	2	2	0	0	0	3	0	11
VILABS	4	2	7	5	2	2	2	0	0	0	7	0	24
LLSA	1	7.5	0	3.5	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	4
TUE	1.5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	1.5
McGill	0.5	0	0	0	4	3.5	0	4.70	0	0	0	0	1
UDEM	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.5

Table 4 VITALISE Partners' Effort per Work Package

2.6 General provisions on eligibility of activities

The Grant Agreement signed by the VITALISE consortium (Nr. 101007990) specifies the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to beneficiaries. The activities funded are the ones described in Annex 1 (Part A and Part B) of the Grant Agreement.

2.6.1 Eligible Activities

The eligible activities of the VITALISE project are defined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and entail all necessary actions by the consortium in order to successfully implement the project.

VITALISE partners may consult the terms and conditions set out in “Chapter 4 - Rights and Obligations of the parties” of the Grant Agreement, as well as, the Project Handbook within the present deliverable, and D1.8 Management Handbook, in order to achieve effective implementation of the project. ENOLL, as the Coordinator of VITALISE, will be coordinating the activities as planned and will be supporting collaboration and communication of VITALISE partners. In any circumstances or events that affect the partnership and the implementation of the VITALISE project, an amendment of the Grant Agreement may be requested.

2.6.2 Eligible Costs

The eligible costs of the VITALISE project are defined in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement. There exist 2 types of costs, namely Direct and Indirect costs.

Direct costs have 3 possible forms of costs in Captain:

- A. Direct personnel costs.
- B. Direct costs of subcontracting.
- D. Other direct costs.

Indirect costs are calculated on the basis of a flat-rate applied (25%) to direct costs excluding direct costs of subcontracting.

The total estimated eligible costs of VITALISE are reimbursed in 100% when the action is implemented in accordance with the Grant Agreement, and it cannot exceed the amount specified as “Maximum grant amount” in Annex 2.

VITALISE consortium partners having signed the Grant Agreement Nr. 101007990 have agreed on terms and conditions relevant to the eligible costs. The relevant Articles on the Grant Agreement are Article 4, Article 5 and Article 6.

Further explanations can be found in the Annotated Model Grant Agreement (available at http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf). The Annotated Model Grant Agreement serves as a user guide that aims to explain terms and conditions by avoiding legal references and technical vocabulary in order to assist beneficiaries to find practical guidelines for the successful implementation of the projects. Further to that, VITALISE consortium partners are encouraged to contact the Coordinating institution (ENoLL), and request advice and support in questions related to the eligibility of costs. The Coordinator will be seeking the answers within the Annotated Model Grant Agreement and by communicating with the Project Officer appointed by the European Commission.

In any circumstances or events that affect the financial management of the VITALISE project, an amendment of the Grant Agreement may be requested, if necessary, according to the rules set in Article 4 of the Grant Agreement.

3 Project management structure

3.1 Consortium

The VITALISE consortium (Figure 2) consists of 19 partners from 11 countries. The consortium as whole has excellent experience in all the tasks defined for VITALISE. In particular, the partners provide the project with scientific (AUTH, LAUREA, LICALAB, VICOM, CERTH, AIT, UPM, TUE, McGill, UDEM), technical (AUTH, VICOM, CERTH, UPM, WITA, VILABS), policy making (ENoLL, LAUREA, UPM, LLSA, TUE), Living Labs methodologies (ENoLL, AUTH, LAUREA, INTRAS, TREBAG, GAIA, AIT, UPM, LLSA, TUE, McGill, UDEM), innovation and exploitation (SIT, VILABS, AV) experience.

The academic partners (AUTH, LAUREA, UPM, LICALAB, TUE, AIT, McGill and UDEM) know already the pain of the lack of open and harmonized access to research infrastructure in the Health and Wellbeing domain. This justifies why this proposal became attractive even for International Partners (McGill and UDEM), working towards realising the VITALISE vision. In addition, technical expertise is required to develop the individual modules of the VITALISE system and to integrate

them into a first prototype that can be used in JRAs. Apart from the Living Lab procedures, the scientific partners will conduct research beyond the state of the art on 3 challenging domains (rehabilitation, transitions in care and smart living environments).

Ethical, legal and regulatory requirements will be taken into account by design. This led the consortium for move from the concept of “Open Data” to the concept of “Open Data for Processing” towards addressing most of the concerns of the participants as well as the researchers towards opening data. Finally, highly specialised expertise in system integration (VICOM, WITA, CERTH) must be leveraged to integrate these technical modules and design considerations into a stable platform.

In the following table the list of partners together with the corresponding representative contact detail are listed:

Figure 2 Consortium partners across the world

Short name	Organisation	Country	Reference person	E-mail
ENoLL	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	BE	Evdokimos Konstantinidis	evdokimosk@enoll.org
AUTH	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	EL	Panagiotis Bamidis	bamidis@med.auth.gr
LAUREA	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	FI	Teemu Santonen	Teemu.Santonen@laurea.fi
LICALAB	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	BE	Vicky Van der Auwera	vicky.vanderauwera@thomasmore.be
INTRAS	FUNDACION INTRAS	ES	Rosa Almeida	rra@intras.es
TREBAG	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES	HU	Eniko Nagy	eniko.nagy@trebag.hu
GAIA	SOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE	ES	Jokin Garatea	garatea@gaia.es
VICOM	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	ES	Gorka Epelde	gepelde@vicomtech.org
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	EL	Spiros Nikolopoulos	nikolopo@iti.gr
AIT	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AT	Peter Fröhlich	Peter.frohelic@ait.ac.at
SIT	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	IT	Valentina Conotter	valentina.conotter@socialit.it
UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES	Beatriz Merino	bmerino@lst.tfo.upm.es
WITA	WITA SRL	IT	Giuseppe Conti	giuseppe.conti@wita.care
AV	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	BG	Adriane Thrash	at@anthologyventures.com
VILABS	VILABS OE	EL	Ilias Trochidis	it@vilabs.eu
LLSA	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	FR	David Servais	david.servais@forumllsa.org

Short name	Organisation	Country	Reference person	E-mail
TUE	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN	NL	Pieter Van Gorp	p.m.e.v.gorp@tue.nl
McGill	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	CA	Eva Kehayia	eva.kehayia@mcgill.ca
UDEM	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	CA	Johanne Higgins	johanne.higgins@umontreal.ca

Table 5 VITALISE Partners' Contact Details

3.2 Roles and entities

Successful collaboration and continuous communication among partners of the project and the parties identified as part of the stakeholder ecosystem, is the key for achieving the project goals. For this reason, specific roles and management entities have been identified:

Project Coordinator (PC) (Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, ENoLL)

The role of the PC is to represent the project and the consortium, report to the Commission, monitor overall project performance, administer project resources and promote project visibility. The PC will chair the Project Steering Board meetings and is responsible for the project formal communication with the Commission and other stakeholders. Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis brings considerable experience in the dual fields of health and technology and as such has experience of managing multipartner research projects. Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis has experience in technical co-ordination of complex IT projects including EC-funded projects and has already successfully co-ordinated 1 large EU projects from the position of the Technical Coordinator (CAPTAIN H2020), while he has worked as deputy technical coordinator of the SmokeFreeBrain H2020.

Technical co-ordinator (TC) (Dr. Gorka Epelde, VICOM)

The role of the Technical co-ordinator is to audit the R&D performance of the project and ensure accomplishment of the technical objectives. The TC is responsible for resolving work implementation problems and dead ends, and is also the direct link between the Project Management Board and the people performing the work helping to bridge communications between technical and clinical parties. Dr. Gorka Epelde worked as a researcher in various FP6, FP7 and H2020 projects and has coordinated several regional and national projects as well as supported EU projects coordination as VICOM team and WP leader (e.g. H2020 MIDAS, FP7 Si-Elegans, FP6 i2Home, FP6 Vital).

Scientific co-ordinator (SC) (Prof. Panos Bamidis, AUTH)

The role of the Scientific co-ordinator is to audit the Joint Research Activities performance of the project and ensure accomplishment of the scientific objectives Prof Bamidis has experience of managing multi-partner research projects. Prof. Bamidis has already successfully coordinated 4 large EU projects (Long Lasting Memories, EPBLNet, MEdicator and ChildrenHealth).

VITALISE Harmonization Body Coordinator (VSBC) (Ms. Despoina Petsani, AUTH)

The role of the VITALISE Harmonization Body Coordinator is to synchronise the goals and the objectives of the specific Harmonization Body, organizing the Harmonization meetings every 6 months as well as ensuring the openness to the global Living Lab and the research community. The VSBC will also advise the coordination of the Harmonization Body built in T2.3 and run throughout the project's lifecycle.

Transnational Access Manager (TAM) (Dr. Valentina Conotter, SIT)

The role of the Transnational Access Call Manager is to manage the transnational access open calls for external researchers. The TACM will ensure that all the processes of calls, applications eligibility and selection, evaluation committees and all the relevant processes will run smoothly and on time.

Quality and Risk Manager (QRM) (Apostolos Vontas, VILABS)

The Quality and Risk Manager is responsible for enforcing monitoring and assessment of the project's quality. The QRM reports to the PC (Project coordinator). Apostolos Vontas has several years' experience in management and coordination roles within large EC-funded projects.

Work Package Leaders (WPL)

Each WP has an assigned leader who will be in charge of coordinating activities of their WP, execute fine-grained plans and allow monitoring of the activities of the WP. WPL's report to the PC, QRM, or TM depending on the nature of the issues. WPLs are further supported by Task Leaders.

WP nr.	Main Responsible	Contact	Deputy	Contact
WP1	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)	francesca.spagnoli@enoll.org	Marc Bouchet (ENoLL)	marc.bouchet@enoll.org
WP2	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	evdokimosk@enoll.org	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	despoinapets@gmail.com, petsanid@auth.gr
WP3	Gorka Epelde (VICOMTECH)	gepelde@vicomtech.org	Michail Timoleon (AUTH)	mtimoleon@auth.gr
WP4	Ines Vaittinen (ENoLL)	ines.vaittinen@enoll.org	Leidy Vanessa Enriquez (ENoLL)	leidyenriquez@enoll.org
WP5	Vicky Van der Auwera (LiCALAB)	vicky.vanderauwera@thomasmore.be	Nele De Witte (LiCALAB)	nele.dewitte1@thomasmore.be
WP6	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	despoinapets@gmail.com, petsanid@auth.gr	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	evdokimosk@enoll.org

WP nr.	Main Responsible	Contact	Deputy	Contact
WP7	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)	Teemu.Santonen@laurea.fi	Mikko Julin (LAUREA)	mikko.julin@laurea.fi
WP8	Jokin Garatea (GAIA)	garate@gaia.es	Idoia Munoz (GAIA)	idoia@gaia.es
WP9	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	despoinapets@gmail.com, petsanid@auth.gr	Despoina Mantziari (AUTH)	mantziad@gmail.com
WP10	Rosa Almeida (INTRAS)	rra@intras.es	Raquel Losada Duràn (INTRAS)	rld@intras.es
WP11	Valentina Conotter (SocialIT)	valentina.conotter@socialit.it	Irene Facchin (SocialIT)	irene.facchin@socialit.it
WP12	Alejandro Medrano (UPM)	amedrano@lst.tfo.upm.es	Samanta Villanueva Mascato (UPM)	svillanueva@lst.tfo.upm.es
WP13	Ilias Trochidis (VILABS)	it@vilabs.eu	Ada Pellumbaj (VILABS)	adapel@vilabs.eu
WP14	Panagiotis Kartsidis (AUTH)	panos.kartsidis@gmail.com	Leidy Vanessa Enriquez (ENoLL)	leidyenriquez@enoll.org

Table 6 VITALISE Work Package Leaders

Research Infrastructure Leaders (RIL)

Responsible for the daily management of the research infrastructures. Each Living Lab partner will designate a research infrastructure leader for each of the infrastructures provided by the Living Lab.

The Project Management Board (PMB)

Together the Project, Technical, Scientific, Quality-Risk and VITALISE Harmonization Body Coordinator co-ordinators and WP1 leader make up the Project Management Board (PMB) to manage and guide the VITALISE project. The PMB has responsibility for monitoring the overall research activities and technical progress and direction of the project. It is also responsible for the resources used, the costs incurred as well as risk evaluation and will be accountable for the project's Ethical Assessment.

The Harmonization Board (SB)

Led by the VITALISE Harmonization Body Coordinator is composed of one main representative of each Living Lab in the consortium, the RIL, QRM, SC and PC, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The Project Steering Board (PSB)

This is made up of the PC, TC, SC, VSBC, QRM, work package leaders and a representative from each consortium member. A Data Controller role will also be included. The PSB is responsible for holistic decision making within the project and ensuring the overall aims and objectives of VITALISE are achieved.

Project Steering Board
Project Coordinator (Evdokimos Konstantinidis)
Technical Coordinator (Gorka Epelde)
Scientific Coordinator (Panagiotis Bamidis)
VITALISE Harmonization Body Coordinator (Despoina Petsani)
Quality and Risk Manager (Apostolos Vontas)
WP1 Leader (Francesca Spagnoli)
WP2 Leader (Evdokimos Konstantinidis)
WP3 Leader (Gorka Epelde)
WP4 Leader (Ines Vaittinen)
WP5 Leader (Vicky Van der Auwera)
WP6 Leader (Despoina Petsani)
WP7 Leader (Teemu Santonen)
WP8 Leader (Jokin Garatea)
WP9 Leader (Despoina Petsani)
WP10 Leader (Rosa Almeida)
WP11 (Valentina Conotter)
WP12 Leader (Alejandro Medrano)

Project Steering Board
WP13 Leader (Ilias Trochidis)
WP14 Leader (Panagiotis Kartsidis)
Data Controller (Leidy Vanessa Enriquez Florez)

Table 7 VITALISE Project Steering Board

An Ethical Board (EB)

This is in the form of a group of experts from within and without the consortium with multidisciplinary competences (ethics, privacy, security, finance, etc) that will be called upon whenever a relevant issue rises.

Ethical Board
Panagiotis Bamids (AUTH)
Eva Kehayia (McGill)
Vicky Van der Auwera (LicaLab)
Jokin Garatea (GAIA)
Panagiotis Kartsidis (AUTH)

Evaluators Board (EvB)

It will consist of SC, the corresponding RIL based on the proposal and one independent evaluator that will be selected based on the research expertise. The RIL and independent evaluator will be responsible for grading the proposals that will be granted Transnational and Virtual access and the SC will monitor the procedure and ensure unbiased evaluation. In case of tied votes, the decision will be taken by the SC.

Advisory Board (AB)

The AB is composed of members, outside the project, being senior researchers, Living Lab managers, entrepreneurs and decision makers with a high reputation in the project domain. The AB will be informed on the project results and progress at regular intervals by peer review of selected deliverables. It will meet twice during the project duration to provide suggestions with respect to the project strategic orientations, project research challenges, business and exploitation direction and project support of user needs. The AB members will sign appropriate confidential agreement prior to any disclosure of confidential information. In case of personnel changes, new members for the above roles will be elected by the PSB. Figure 3.5 shows the management structure and main communication channels for VITALISE.

3.3 Structure

Figure 3 depicts the management structure and main communication channels for VITALISE.

Decision-making process is articulated at three different levels:

Strategic Level: At this level decisions will be taken by the PSB based on requests by one of the beneficiaries or the PC. PSB meetings will be called upon with at least 15 days of advance notice and may be held online to minimize travel costs. Ordinary meetings will occur in the context of project meetings.

Management Level: Decisions on activities to be carried across different WPs will be discussed during technical meetings which will be called with at least 5 days of advance notice and may be held online. Ordinary meetings will be held in the context of project meetings.

Operational Level: These decisions will not require official meetings and will be taken by internal working groups under coordination of the respective task leaders. The other partners will be informed via emails or during project meetings. Regarding conflict resolution the PC will try to minimize conflict, and should it arise, act to minimize its effect through arbitration with the involved partners. In extreme circumstances a meeting with involved parties shall be called. Should the issue remain unsolved, the PSB will be called upon to resolve it. As a last resort, in case of extreme issues, the PSB may resort to informing the Project Officer. In case of personnel changes, new members for the above roles will be elected by the PSB.

Figure 3 VITALISE management structure

3.4 Methodology

The management methodology will be written down in a reference document titled “Management Handbook” that will document directives and indications about the following topics:

Internal Document Management Tool: To accomplish the management of the project documents including reports, all project members will use a web-based Document Management Tool (MS Teams) supported by the TC and QRM.

Reporting: The PC will ensure regular project reporting and according to EC rules. In both quarterly and yearly reports, the WP Leaders will create the report at the end of each reporting period, based on the feedback from the people working in it describing the status of the WP, the work done, the deliverables released, deviations, etc. The TC will create an overall report which will be approved by the PC. Submission and management of reports will be done through the Document Management Tool (MS Teams).

Meetings – Communication: The project was launched by a plenary kick-off meeting. The meeting was the first opportunity to share the work plan resulting from the negotiation process, to refine the common and shared understanding of tasks and resources to project development and to build up an operational team spirit among VITALISE participants. The partners and PMB shall convene as necessary and at least every four months, in order to provide quick and efficient response to the events that shall arise during the project. If the circumstances allow for it, PMB can meet using

remote meeting technology. In parallel to plenary consortium meetings a series of working meetings for specific scientific and technical issues will take place. Given the nature and the complexity of the project, the consortium may decide to support a series of joint meetings (intra-WP and cross-WP) to speed up the development and integration process, as well as to foster the execution of the pilots. In order to closely monitor the work progress, the TC will organize regular monthly tele-conferences with the WP Leaders.

Quality Assurance Procedure and Assessment: All generated documents must follow a procedure to be finally approved. In internal peer reviews, selected partners will evaluate the quality of all deliverables and such partners will be mentioned on the deliverables. In certain cases, some additional reviews of selected key deliverables will be done by either the AB or by other external reviewers, to ensure the overall quality of the project. Self-assessment of project progress aims to achieve an overall evaluation of the quality and outcome of the work done, ensuring high quality standards in the work carried out and addressing potential problems encountered during the project development. The self-assessment of the project is an iterative process that will be based on the following feedbacks: a) self-assessment of work done by WP leaders and technical project staff, b) project evaluation activities, c) risk assessment, d) input from the AB and e) peer reviewers.

Conflict Resolution: The procedures described above are designed to minimise the chances of conflicts. Nevertheless, should any conflict arise, the first step towards resolution would be for the PC to discuss the problem with the involved parts in order to seek amicable settlement. If a resolution is not achieved, then a majority vote of the PMB will settle the issue. In case of non-performance of any of the partners, the PMB shall have the power to exclude the offending partner by a vote of unanimity minus one. In such circumstances, the provisions of the Grant Agreement guidelines will apply as well as relevant non-conflicting provisions made in the CA. However, before using these procedures, the PMB members will make the largest possible use of their proven negotiation skills.

3.4.1 Online meetings' tool and file sharing

Teleconferencing (audio- or video-based) will be used for organising virtual meetings. For this reason, the Skype software may be used for meetings with only a few participants, while wider project online meetings will be taking place using **Microsoft Teams** set up by the coordinating institution. Files will also be shared among partners by using this channel.

3.4.2 E-mail communication

Mailing lists are set up as an alternative way of communication within the project. In order to prevent redundant and excessive communication, partners should choose the most appropriate communication channel, i.e., the Teams channel. The VITALISE Project mailing list is vitalise@enoll.org and another mailing list was created to serve the JRAs organization (vitalise-jras@enoll.org)

3.5 Project Meetings

Project meetings are important for effective communication among partners and for achieving all the project's objectives. Throughout VITALISE, project duration a series of plenary Consortium meetings, technical meetings and online regular teleconferences will be organised. The types of meetings and their short descriptions are presented in the sections below.

3.5.1 Consortium Plenary Meetings

The main communication and collaboration opportunity in VITALISE is the Consortium Plenary Meetings. They will be conducted on a regular basis (every 6 months), and all partners must be represented, as this is a contractual obligation. Plenary meetings will be hosted, in turn, by the participating institutions. Also, they may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote if needed.

Consortium meetings will serve to present the current work in progress, the work to be done, schedule next actions, present technical issues to be dealt with, and find solutions, as well as to promote collaboration between partners, deal with integration issues and update the project vision. Consortium meetings may also be held by teleconference or other telecommunication means. The Advisory Board members shall be allowed to participate in Consortium meetings upon invitation but shall not have any voting rights.

3.5.2 Project Steering Board meetings

Opportunities or occasions for PSB meetings shall be selected in accordance with the provisions set in the VITALISE consortium agreement. Project Steering Board meetings may be co-hosted with Consortium Plenary Meetings, but they may also be held by teleconference or other telecommunication means.

3.5.3 Technical or WP meetings

Apart from Plenary Meetings, partners may decide to organize and hold face-to-face meetings focused on the works of a specific Work Package, or a selection of tasks (either scientific, or technical or other) to enable successful collaboration and communication between partners and speed up the development and integration processes. In any such event, the Consortium as a whole should be informed, and either the Project Coordinator, or Project Manager or Technical Coordinator should try to attend in order to ensure effective coordination with other partners and tasks.

3.5.4 WP leaders teleconferencing

VITALISE introduces the “Stand-Up meetings” that will take place online (teleconferences) and be run every month. These are quick update meetings which are not expected to last more than 15 minutes. All partners are encouraged to join, however, only the WP leaders will be updating on the progress of each WP. The Planner tool of MS Teams will be used to report updates and facilitate the Stand-Up meetings and will be included under each WP in the Microsoft Teams platform. The notes in the Planner will be considered as the minutes of the meeting.

3.5.5 WP teleconferencing

The WP leaders are encouraged to adopt Stand-Up meetings for their respective Work Packages task coordination. In this case, online documents, split in Tasks and sub-tasks (if required), shall be produced and used. The online-shared documents (in Microsoft Teams) will be considered as the minutes of the meeting.

3.6 Project website

The website of the project should be informative, user-friendly and accessible and should engage simple language without technical and highly sophisticated terms. The same principles apply for the project brochure, press kit and videos. All the important information will be made available through the project web site (<https://www.vitalise-project.eu>) including:

- Project background.
- Objectives.

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

- Living Lab infrastructures.
- Expected outcomes and target groups.
- List of beneficiaries.
- Public documents, including deliverables.
- News regarding the project and events organised by the consortium.
- Other information of relevance to the consortium.

4 Document management

4.1 Classification of Documents

Deliverables (which include documents), must always be classified in the following dissemination level categories, using one of the following codes, as stated in the GA:

- PU: Public.
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the EC Services).
- EU-RES: Classified information: RESTRAINT UE (EC decision 2005/444/EC).
- EU-CON: Classified information: CONFIDENTIAL UE (EC decision 2005/444/EC).
- EU-SEC: Classified information: SECRET UE (EC decision 2005/444/EC).

The VITALISE project will involve no activities or results raising security issues and no 'EU-classified' information as background or results. Therefore, all deliverables of the project will be either PU or CO, as seen in Annex I of the GA.

4.2 Document standards

4.2.1 Allowed document types

Working documents intended for subsequent modification by partners should be produced using Microsoft Office (preferably version 2007 or later). Final versions of documents (e.g., internal and public deliverables) should be published as .PDF documents (compatible with Adobe Acrobat 7.0 or later). All other (graphics, audio and video) files should be based on recognized standards: .JPG, .PNG, .GIF, .TIFF, .PPT etc.

4.2.2 Format and style guidelines

Each document should include the following sections:

- A document-specific cover page: this shall include the title of the document, the main author(s), dates of interest and the version of the document.
- A following page with, amongst others, details on the Project ID, the dissemination level of the document, all contributing authors and an abstract- keywords section (in case the document is a deliverable - report).
- The Table of Contents (ToC).
- Abbreviations List (where applicable).
- An Executive summary.
- The Main body of the text: All sections of the main body of the text should be clearly defined. Section headings, titles and subtitles should be used to structure the document and help the reader maintain an overview of what is being addressed and at what level of detail. Used in conjunction with the ToC, relevant sections can easily be identified for ease of browsing. Figures, tables and graphs contained in the body of the document should be properly explained and their relevance clearly demonstrated. Discussion documents that are not fully formatted should at least clearly distinguish between main sections, titles and running text.
- References and (where applicable) Annexes - Appendices.
- Styles and colour schemes provided in the document templates should be followed.

Documents that are deliverables (reports), should be named accordingly, with additional numbers for version updates and standard suffixes to indicate the format of the document, as stated in Section

4.3 below. The final version of the document should be made available as a .PDF document. For intermediate versions of the document, Microsoft Word (or Microsoft PowerPoint) files shall be provided, since these are much easier to annotate.

Furthermore, under 29.4 of the GA, any dissemination of results (in any form) must display the EU emblem. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Apart from the emblem, the following text should be included: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007990". For draft versions of a document prepared by authors of different sites, it is advisable to include authors' names for each section, as an annotation, to facilitate communication between interested parties.

4.2.3 Compliance with Data Protection Guidelines

The Final Deliverables which are specified as "PU: Public" will be uploaded on the Project Website following a data protection quality check and adequate editing of the document. This revision or editing of the document will allow the consortium to fulfil the requirements or comply with regulations set by the EU data protection law, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) which is expected to come into force in May 2018.

4.3 Versioning

The development of a document is supervised by the person responsible for the deliverable [member of the Lead Beneficiary as in the Description of Action (DoA)], who will be responsible for assigning subsections to other contributors, for providing clear instructions and defining deadlines, for integrating sections into the main document and for maintaining the appropriate version control.

When elaborating a document, three types of intermediate versions of this document may be produced:

- Working/discussion document setting out main headlines and some elaboration on specific topics.
- Full draft with all the sections nearly complete.
- Ready-for-review version provided to the internal reviewers for major/minor comments and changes.
- Pre-final version available only for minor changes and to be circulated among the VITALISE partners and provided to the PC for final approval, before submitting the document as a deliverable to the EC.

Each of these versions may require more than one round of feedback before the final version is achieved. To communicate and log detailed changes in the document, the Microsoft Word Revision Mode – recording and tracking all changes – should be switched on when modifying the document. The amended version should be uploaded onto the file repository with appropriate naming. These changes will be integrated into the current version by the person responsible for the deliverable.

The numbering of versions shall be made as follows:

- Version 0.00 to 0.XX for draft versions of working documents
- Version 1.00 for the version submitted for internal review
- Version 2.00 for the version submitted following reviews and relevant revisions
- Version 3.00 for the version uploaded to the European Commission portal
- Version "3.00_Open" for the version uploaded to the VITALISE website taking into account Data Protection Regulation

4.4 Templates

The following templates for the VITALISE project documents have been created and made available to the partners:

- Deliverable template

- Deliverable review report template
- Presentation template
- Financial Report template

4.5 Other documents

Throughout the course of the VITALISE project, a variety of reports and presentations will be produced. These documents should respect the guidelines outlined below.

4.5.1 Publications

Publications are documents that describe technologies, algorithms or methodologies developed within the project. These documents can be: scientific articles, papers, book chapters, books, posters or slide presentations/talks in conferences, Ph.D. thesis and similar documents, public reports, press releases, news articles.

Submission of papers for publications at conferences, journals or media should have the consent of VITALISE Consortium as a whole. For this reason, intention to submit a publication should be communicated to the consortium at the earliest possible date. The procedure outlined below is intended to verify that no paper is submitted without consortium knowledge, that the project is not misrepresented and that no confidential material is inadvertently made public. This could become critic, and eventually generate damage, in case of one or more partners willing to patent information that is then disclosed. More specifically:

- Partners must inform the Coordinator and the WP13 Leader of planned dissemination activities within the project context at least 30 days before the date of publication according to the CA.
- Essential information with regard to the publication, such as title, name(s) of author(s), short summary, release date, where to be published and name of contact person should be provided.
- A copy of the publication should be uploaded to the Open Project VITALISE document section before submission for comments by partners. Information about the title, authors, conference/journal/media to be published, expected date of submission/publication, contact person and deadline for comments should be provided.
- Partners should also provide the SC with a copy of the publication, for project documentation and dissemination via the project website.
- Partners who want to use other partners' knowledge, pre-existing know-how etc., in own publications have to officially request consent to such publications by the corresponding partner.

No strict procedures can be defined for authorship. It is the responsibility of all partners to respect standard collegial practices when deciding on number and order of authors. When presenting global project results, input from all relevant sites should be acknowledged. In case of conflict or suspicion of abuse, the matter should be brought to the attention of the PC and the PSB. Any use of the EU emblem within publications must follow the official guidelines. These guidelines include instructions regarding the obligation prescribed by the contract to publicly acknowledge the support received from the European Union. Additional information can be found in the official website of the European Commission as "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020". More practical information will be also presented in D1.8 Management Handbook.

4.5.2 Reports and presentation

Each partner is free to produce reports and give presentations on their work throughout the VITALISE project. The funding sources and acknowledgement of the Project should be included. The reports and presentations should be made available to partners upon request.

5 Project reporting and financing

5.1 General procedures and rules for project reporting

As specified in the VITALISE Grant Agreement, the Coordinator must submit to the Commission technical and financial reports.

5.1.1 Reporting Periods

The official reporting periods of the VITALISE project are the following:

- Reporting Period 1: from month 1 to month 18, i.e. from April 2021 to September 2022.
- Reporting Period 2: from month 19 to month 36, i.e. from October 2022 to March 2022.

The periodic reports include:

- A Technical report (in 2 parts, one in a structured form from the grant management system and the second in a free text form describing the progress towards the project objectives).
- A Financial report consisting of individual partner financial statements, an explanation of the use of resources and a periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

Official reports will be submitted by beneficiaries into the Participant Portal of the European Commission.

5.1.2 Reporting process

The reporting procedure consists of several steps that have been defined:

- Partners (beneficiaries) must write and submit six-month reports. These need to include periodic report contributions concerning their institution dissemination and exploitation activities (carried out within the respective reporting period) and administrative aspects. Finally, they should keep a record of Time Sheets of their team members.
- WP Leaders must submit a description of the work progress carried out in their WP to be used for the Periodic Progress Reports. WP Leaders are responsible for gathering the necessary information, i.e., scientific contributions from partners themselves. WP Leaders should therefore ensure and support a well-functioning communication structure within their working group.
- The Coordinating institution is responsible for the compilation of the various contributions into a central document, which will be submitted to the European Commission.

5.1.3 Financial Report Template

VITALISE Grant Agreement no. 101007990										
Select Periodic Report										
Select Partner										
Personnel Costs		Travel					Equipment, Consumables, Audit Costs			
Direct personnel costs	PM	Actual Amount	Travel costs			Amount	Software and software licences costs		Dissemination Material	
			Description	Event Description	Destination		Description	Amount	Description	Amount
WP1	Management	0,00								
WP2	NA1- Common standards, procedures and practices	0,00								
WP3	NA2- Implementation, Improvement and optimized use of the H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools	0,00								
WP4	NA3- Capacity Building and Training	0,00								
WP5	JRA1 - Rehabilitation supported by technology	0,00					Total Webinar Licences costs	- €	Total Dissemination Material	- €
WP6	JRA2 - Transitional care						Equipment rental/buying (nursing, IT equipment, etc.)		External services (e.g. insurance, security fees, quality control)	
WP7	JRA3- Everyday living environments	0,00					Description	Amount	Description	Amount
WP8	TA1 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for rehabilitation	0,00								
WP9	TA2 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care	0,00								
WP10	TA3- TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living	0,00								
WP11	NA4- Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection	0,00					Total Travel costs			
WP12	VA1 - Virtual Access to datasets						Travel & Subsistence for transnational access costs		Total cost of equipment rental	- €
WP13	Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability	0,00					Description	Amount	Maintenance costs (e.g. power supply, etc.)	Total Direct Costs
WP14	Ethics requirements									Indirect Costs
		0,00					Description	Amount		Costs for Subcontracting
Total Personnel							Total travel & subsistence for transnational access costs		Total maintenance costs	- €
										Total

Figure 4 Financial report template

5.1.4 Effort Report Template

VITALISE Grant Agreement no. 101007990						
WP1	Management	Start	End	ENoLL	M1-M9	M10-M18
		1	36	18,00		0
T1.1	Project coordination and consortium management	1	36	10,00		
T1.2	Operational management and quality/risk control and ethical issues	1	36	3,00		
T1.3	Financial management and reporting	1	36	3,00		
T1.4	Ethical and security management	1	36	0,50		
T1.5	Data management	1	36	0,50		
T1.6	Innovation management	1	36	1,00		
WP2	NA1- Common standards, procedures and practices	1	36	14,00	0	0
T2.1	Initial analysis of Living Lab existing processes and services	1	10	3,00		
T2.2	Harmonization board and body meetings	1	36	6,00		
T2.3	Establishment of evaluation process and tools	1	12	4,00		
T2.4	User requirements for ICT tools	6	24	1,00		
WP3	NA2- Implementation, improvement and optimized use of the H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools	2	36	3,50	0	0
T3.1	Service architecture definition, federation authentication and integration	4	18			
T3.2	Extensible VITALISE data model	2	24			
T3.3	Living Lab infrastructure API and core communication modules	4	28			
T3.4	Anonymisation mechanism and synthetic data engine toolkit development	6	16			
T3.5	RAI Cloud server	6	22			
T3.6	RAI Certified Node dataset curation, preservation and provision of access for Living Lab access	6	22			
T3.7	Panel management tool	4	16			
T3.8	VITALISE Portal for data discovery and federated data access	6	22	0,50		
T3.9	VITALISE SDKs	8	30			
T3.10	Infrastructure tools deployment on each Living Lab	10	30	1,00		
T3.11	EOSC services reuse and VITALISE as EOSC service	4+12	25+32	2,00		
WP4	NA3- Capacity Building and Training	4	36	17,00	0,00	0,00
T4.1	Organisation of summer schools for young researchers	6	32	5,00		
T4.2	Online educational material and training programmes	4	36	4,00		
T4.3	Enlarging the community	6	36	4,00		
T4.4	Fast track training	16	34	2,00		
T4.5	Design and implementation of common postgraduate courses	12	36	1,00		
T4.6	Boosting commercialization potential of researchers results	10	36	1,00		
WP5	JRA1 - Rehabilitation supported by technology	2	36	3,00	0,00	0,00
T5.1	Refinement of the Research protocol	2	12			
T5.2	Preparation, planning and ethics	6	14			
T5.3	Research activities in real-life environment	12	36	1,00		
T5.4	Results and analysis	21	36	2,00		
WP6	JRA2 - Transitional care	2	36	3,00	0,00	0,00
T6.1	Refinement of the Research protocol	2	12			
T6.2	Preparation, planning and ethics	6	14			
T6.3	Research activities in real-life environment	12	36	1,00		
T6.4	Results and analysis	12	36	2,00		
WP7	JRA3- Everyday living environments	2	36	3,00	0,00	0,00
T7.1	Refinement of the Research protocol	1	12			
T7.2	Preparation, planning and ethics	6	14			
T7.3	Research activities in real-life environment	12	36	1,00		
T7.4	Results and analysis	21	36	2,00		
WP8	TA1 - TA to Living Lab Infrastructures for rehabilitation	18	36	0,00	0,00	0,00
T8.1	AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab	18	36			
T8.2	Thomas More gaitlab - Mobilab	18	36			
T8.3	GAIA and Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation	18	36			
T8.4	INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab	18	36			
T8.5	Laurea simulated hospital	18	36			
T8.6	McGill CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab	18	36			

Figure 5 Effort report template example

5.1.5 Currency

Financial statements must be drafted in euro. Beneficiaries and linked third parties with accounting established in a currency other than the euro must convert the costs recorded in their accounts into euro, at the average of the daily exchange rates published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union, calculated over the corresponding reporting period.

If no daily euro exchange rate is published in the Official Journal of the European Union for the currency in question, they must be converted at the average of the monthly accounting rates published on the Commission's website, calculated over the corresponding reporting period.

6 QUALITY ASSESSMENT

In this Section, the Quality Assessment Plan (QAP) of the VITALISE project is presented. The aim of the QAP is to provide a set of requirements and standards, as well as to specify control procedures and actions that will assure the high quality of project deliverables and project management. More specifically, the quality expectations for project deliverables, the responsibilities of project partner, quality control procedures to ensure their implementation and the strategy to deal with possible risks are defined.

6.1 Quality expectations

First, the expectations regarding the quality of the project deliverables, as well as the expectations concerning the project management are presented. In general, the quality of a given deliverable can be recognized by the presence of: efficiency, feasibility and sustainability. VITALISE deliverables can be classified in the following three categories:

- Documents/Reports (R): Documents should follow a consistent format; thus, a document template has been generated and will be used throughout the project.
- Demonstrator, pilot, prototypes (DEM): These deliverables include software components that should comply with user requirements, in terms of functionality, performance and stability, defined in detail in deliverables D3.1 “VITALISE Service specification” and D3.2 “RAI Service specification”. Furthermore, software components should allow for extensibility and reusability to simplify the process of adding new features or adjusting functionality. Another key aspect of the software quality is proper documentation, which includes English documentation in the source code to support the developers, as well as detailed user manuals to guide the end- users.
- Other.

In total, as listed in Section 2.4, there are 60 deliverables in the VITALISE project (51 of them of type "R", 1 of type "DEM" and 8 of type "OTHER"). The common quality expectation of all deliverables is their on-time delivery according to the project work plan.

Project management is effective when it assures that the project progress follows the work plan agreed. For this to happen, project progresses –both technical and financial- need to frequently be documented and there must be no delay in the communication with the EC or in the resolution of plausible technical and financial issues. In order to ensure this, Gantt charts, based on the deliverables list (Annex I of the GA) will be produced and periodic project management meetings may be held if needed (preferably as side-meetings during technical meetings to reduce travel costs). The minutes of these meetings will be recorded and distributed among partners.

6.2 Quality responsibilities of consortium members

The PC has a plethora of responsibilities, which are vital for ensuring the proper quality of the project, either by facilitating communication among partners and ensuring their up-to-date information, or by guaranteeing the proper quality of documents.

In particular, the PC is responsible for:

- Monitoring compliance of partners to their obligations.
- Submitting the other partners' project deliverables and all other documents required by the GA to the EU in time, in case one or more partners are late in submitting them.
- Keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available.
- Transmitting documents and information related to the project to any other party concerned.
- Providing, upon request, partners with official copies or originals of documents, which are in the sole possession of the PC when such copies or originals are necessary for partners to present claims.

- Collecting, reviewing (to verify consistency) and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the EU.

Moreover, under article 17.2 of the GA, each partner must immediately inform the PC, who, in turn, must immediately inform the EC and other partners in case of events which are likely to significantly affect or delay the implementation of the project, such as changes in its legal, financial, technical, and organisational or ownership situation.

6.3 Quality assurance and quality control process

In this Section, the quality assurance and quality control processes to be followed are described, so that the quality expectations presented in Section 6.1 are realized.

6.3.1 Quality assurance for Deliverables

The quality of deliverables is assured by providing templates and guidelines to the individuals working on different parts of the project.

Documents

Standard templates shall be used for project documents (deliverables, reports, presentations, minutes, etc.). These templates can be found in the Microsoft Teams repository of VITALISE. All documents to be sent to the EC or released to the public shall be generated using these templates.

Software components

In order to ensure quality of software components, careful consideration shall be taken within VITALISE so as to meet the following demands:

- compliance of software components with the user requirements and,
- usability of the developed software for Living Labs and external researchers.

6.3.2 Quality control of deliverables

In order to ensure the timely production and the quality of the deliverables, all deliverables will be internally reviewed. Some of them may be reviewed externally as well. The following process will apply:

- Partners responsible for each deliverable are already defined in the DoA document of the VITALISE project. A person responsible for the deliverable (DR) is designated by the partner.
- Initially, the DR will define the potential contributors (with the help of the WP Leader and partners, if needed). Then, the DR and the contributors will agree upon the Table of Contents (ToC), as well as agree upon the sub-tasks each contributor will take care of. The DR and the contributors will also agree upon a provisional calendar. Both the ToC and the provisional calendar should be communicated to the PC at least 6 weeks before the deliverable deadline.
- Internal Reviewers (two per deliverable) have already been assigned for all deliverables taking into account their expertise. For some strategic deliverables, the decision to submit to external reviewers (chosen outside the project) can be taken by the PC in collaboration with DR and WP Leader. If requested even by one contributor, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) will be signed.
- The contributions will be made by contributors (deadlines being under the responsibility of DR and contributors) with respect to the provisional calendar. The integration of the contributions is made under the responsibility of the DR.
- When the deliverable reaches a ready-for-review version (at least three weeks before the submission deadline) it will be sent to the internal reviewers by the DR.

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

- The internal reviewers must reply with detailed comments within one week. The reviews are sent to the DR and the PC.
- The PC checks the reviews and decides whether there are major issues or not. If there are major issues, the PC together with the WP Leader and the DR, decide which corrective actions should be followed to deal with the problems. In case of disagreement, the final decision is made by the PSB.
- The DR is responsible for integrating the requested remarks/revisions into an updated version together with a note/email stating how the reviewers' comments or PC's suggestions were addressed (at least one week before the deadline).
- The DR distributes the revised deliverable to the reviewers, to be approved within two days.
- The reviewers inform the DR whether the deliverable is accepted or there are still problems. In the latter case, the above procedure is repeated.
- The final version is submitted for approval to the PC. Potential objections should be raised within 5 days.
- The PC is responsible for submitting the Deliverable to the EC (sending the electronic version to the EC Project Officer and uploading the final version to the File Repository).
- The whole procedure has to be implemented taking into account strict deadlines for each step. These are agreed early on and published for each sub-task in the Open Project platform.
- The EC shall also audit and assess deliverables (under Article 22.1 of the GA).

Specifically, the deliverable submission procedure is defined as follows:

Deliverable submission procedure	
Deadline	30th of the month
Table of contents	1.5 month prior to final submission
First submission	15th of the month
Review	15th to 22nd of the month
Second submission	27th of the month
Review	Until the 30th of the month
Final submission	30th of the month

Table 8 VITALISE Deliverables' submission procedure

Documents

Documents should be checked for style, completeness, presentation and accomplishment of deliverable objectives as described in Part A of the DoA. Documents should also be checked for technically valid, sound and novel contribution (when applicable), completeness of results, and comparison with existing works, etc.

Software components:

The software components are tested and evaluated so as to make sure that user requirements are met.

In particular, the software components that will be produced in WP3 will be tested by Living Labs in WP2 and Joint Research Activities (WP5, WP6, WP7) and by external researchers in Transnational and Virtual Access (WP8, WP9, WP10, WP12)

6.3.3 Quality control of project management

The control of project management shall be implemented by ENoLL central administrative, legal, and financial departments, which have long and significant expertise in EU project participation and coordination activities. ENoLL ensures the ability of the VITALISE project to rapidly start-up and maintain professional management of EU financial and reporting requirements.

6.4 Control of changes

6.4.1 Technical changes

In case any changes of the approaches to the realisation of the technical aspects of the project are needed, a change request will be sent to the TC, who will then discuss the implication of such a change with the proposing party, as well as with the PSB. If the necessity of a major change in the technical approach of a part of the system is agreed, the proposed change will be discussed and approved during the next project meeting. If the requested change is rated as substantial, it will also be reported to the EC Project Officer through the PC.

6.5 Risk management

VITALISE is a consortium consisting of various independent partner organisations. Its complex objectives demand the successful cooperation of many experts from different scientific fields. A successful completion of the project will again heighten the reputation of each partner and the individuals associated with them. Therefore, despite the organisational independence of partners, a successful completion of the problem at hand is in everyone's strongest interest.

Risk management addresses issues that could endanger achievement of critical objectives. Effective risk management has to consider sources for cost, schedule and performance risks, as well as other risks, and specify practices to systematically plan, anticipate and mitigate these risks in order to minimise their impact on the project. In this Section, we describe the risk management processes to identify, analyse and mitigate risks efficiently. The QRM is responsible for coordinating this process.

6.5.1 Risk identification and analysis

The VITALISE implementation (depicted in the table below) ensures that potential risks will be identified within the Harmonization Board and Body activities, the design and pilot phases of the Joint Research Activities as well as the external selected applicants to run their projects, and will be appropriately addressed, minimizing the overall implementation risks. The QRM will be in charge of risk management. In particular, the QRM will be in charge of: i) illustrating potential risks (static and dynamic / recurring) present, together with their date, classification and the impact assessment (features, cost and time); ii) highlighting any opportunity emerging from a risk through a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis; iii) detailing causes and effects of each risks element also with support of dedicated flow charts, influence diagrams or Decision-Tree Diagrams (DTDs); iv) recommending possible allocation of human resources for any necessary mitigating action (preventive or remedial); v) as soon as a risk has been identified and needs to be addressed, the QRM will be responsible for the definition of new project activities necessary to ensure the mitigation of risk, the assignment of the priority level of activity in mitigating the risk index and status of the project and the allocation of human resources required to perform the activities of risk mitigation.

Description	Probability	Impact	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Harmonization process risks				
Only a few Living Labs and researchers join the Harmonization Body	LOW	HIGH	2	The Harmonization Board and Body gives a word to all the Living Labs (beyond ENoLL and EIT Health Living Labs network) which makes it attractive. An invitation to a meeting for health and wellbeing Living Labs last summer in during the OpenLivingLab Days in Greece, made more than 40 Living Lab managers and researcher to meet each other and discuss.
Only a few Living Labs and Researchers participate at the Harmonization meetings	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	2	The Harmonization meetings will take place twice per year during the lifecycle of VITALISE and yearly afterwards. Even if twice per year is considered too frequent (it will allow the evaluation and adaptation of the procedures of VITALISE), one of them will take place as a satellite event of the Open Living Lab Days where more than 400 Living Lab staff and researchers are gathered every year.
Technical risks				
Big Data mechanisms for local storage is not enough to support sharing	LOW	MEDIUM	3	VICOM has experience in big data processing. Many methods will be examined to allow high throughput data collection and sharing. Despite the options at mainstream NO-SQL Databases such as MongoDB, Cassandra, CouchDB, VITALISE will look and work with Time-series oriented DBs (Graphite, InfluxDB, OpenTSDB) as Living Labs data are in the majority time-series oriented.
Technical support required for bug-fixes during the JRAs and the external projects	MEDIUM	HIGH	3	VITALISE devotes a whole WP (WP3) on the design and development of a common Middleware as a collection of APIs and services facilitating and standardizing the common communication protocols among the different hardware and software components. This WP runs throughout the project's lifecycle in order to adapt to the needs of the researchers and the Living Labs, debug and support the JRAs and the external projects.

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

Description	Probability	Impact	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Operational risks				
Insufficient number of Involved participants for the JRAs and the external projects	MEDIUM	HIGH	5,6,7	Participatory Design (PD), the value of Living Labs, implies active involvement and collaboration of the intended users. The Living Labs of the consortium have already a strong and trustful network of collaboration with all the types of stakeholders in the Health and Wellbeing domain and have developed methodologies for participants engagement.
Not enough applications for Transnational access	MEDIUM	HIGH	8, 9, 10, 12	ENoLL, EIT Health Living Labs and Forum LLSA have built a strong network of Living Labs and researchers worldwide. These networks, can easily mobilise academic and industry researchers by many different communication means in order to attract transnational access applications.
Lockdown periods for travels to other countries	LOW	HIGH	8, 9, 10	Although it could be quite not likely to have a travel lockdown period (similar to COVID-19), VITALISE expands its 3-month TA period in 18 months which allows better management.
Project management risks				
Partner/key infrastructure provider leaves the consortium	LOW	HIGH	1	In such an event, the consortium will, in a timely fashion, try to find a replacement organization from outside of the consortium with similar expertise in the respective area. If this is not possible, a replacement within the consortium will be found to take on the responsibilities of the partner leaving.
Disputes within a work-package	LOW	HIGH	1	Where there is sustained disagreement within a work package, which the WP Leader is unable to mediate, the Coordinator will be invited to mediate. In the absence of consensus, the Steering Committee shall be invited to make a decision that is binding.
Disputes within the external projects	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	8, 9 ,10, 12	NDA's and bilateral agreements will be signed between the external projects and the applicants who will be granted

Description	Probability	Impact	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
				access to the infrastructure. SIT will prepare an agreement template that will be circulated to all the partners for amendments.
Security risks				
Issues of ethics, privacy and security	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	1	Laurea and AUTH have specific ethics competences complemented by experts in the Ethics Board. A task (T1.4) has been introduced to manage ethical and security issues.

Table 9 VITALISE risks' identification and measures

6.5.2 Risk monitoring and control

After the identification of potential risks, the spiral approach of the VITALISE implementation ensures that these risks will be appropriately addressed within the following stages, minimising the probability of occurrence. However, there is a need for overall risk monitoring and control, throughout the project. Therefore, the risk status will be reviewed periodically during the Consortium meetings, in order to re-examine possible sources of risks, to uncover risks overlooked and reassess already identified risks. The WP leaders are responsible for identifying and evaluating new risks and communicating them to other partners.

A risk register has been created. Each risk source has been given a probability of occurrence (Low, Medium, or High), level of impact to the project (again Low, Medium, High), and its impact areas are stated (impact to costs, schedule or performance of the project). Risk entries can be added, or currently open risks can be updated or closed.

Depending on the re-assigned priority and consequences of each risk, the PSB decides on further risk handling when monitored risks become critical. Risk handling may range from simple acceptance and monitoring in case a risk is judged as negligible, to development and implementation of risk mitigation plans for risks judged as unacceptable, due to their high impact to the project.

The responsibility for development and implementation of a mitigation plan, in order to reduce the risk to an acceptable level, lies with the associated WP Leader. Risk mitigation plans will address issues, such as the development of alternative courses of action, possible workarounds, schedule for risk handling activities, performance measures on these activities and finally recommended course of action.

After a risk mitigation plan is initiated, the risk will still be monitored, and the progress of open actions will be tracked until completion. Despite all attempts to mitigate a risk, some risks may be unavoidable and become a problem that affects the project. To deal with such risks, project meetings will be scheduled if needed. In these meetings, appropriate response actions will be defined and documented in a contingency plan. The resulting contingency plan will be executed by the responsible partner and monitored by the PSB.

7 Intellectual property right issues

VITALISE will base its Harmonization approach of Living Lab infrastructures in already existing Living Lab's services (processes, methods, techniques, tools) and the design and development of new ICT tools for supporting processes in existing partners expertise and tools. For this reason, special attention will be paid on the knowledge management and Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) of research infrastructures, participating in the study and the JRAs of the project, with respect to all partners and third-parties' previous and new knowledge and IP.

More specifically, the approach to knowledge management and protection is included in VITALISE's Consortium Agreement. The new intellectual property (IP) developed during project's lifecycle will be attributed to all the consortium partners, interested in further exploiting this IP after the project is completed. It is noted that all partners will be given the opportunity to highlight in the Consortium Agreement, their pre-existing IP, which is declared as "Background IP". Further exploitation rules for Ips will be also discussed in D13.3 Innovation Management Report.

7.1 Background

The Background IP will be used as a core resource for the Harmonization of Living Lab infrastructures and the implementation of new ICT tools, during the project lifecycle, but the initial ownership rights will remain solely with the partner during and after the VITALISE project. However, any transformations and use of Background IPs in new contexts, the context of VITALISE's aims, objectives and target groups, will be considered as IP and knowledge produced by and belong to the consortium of the current project. Instead, where such IP rights, including the rights of third parties, exist prior to the start of this agreement or are subsequently developed independently from this agreement, each party shall specify all Background IP it expects to use in the course of this agreement (which is either owned by the party itself or owned by a third-party subject to licenses). All such disclosed lists of Background IP will be collated and inserted in the agreement prior to signing.

7.2 Monitoring of usage

During the project, it is important to monitor the usage of the background information and of the results. The owner will decide the publicity of the background. It should be noted that it is not allowed for the project members to disclose the background information outside of the project without the permission of the owner. The owner will be responsible for the monitoring of usage of the background and of the results produced, e.g., keeping logs of downloads.

As for the access rights to another partner's results or Background IP will only be granted if the requesting partner or the consortium needs that access in order to carry out the project or to use its own results. Any Access Rights are granted on a non-exclusive basis, are worldwide and expressly exclude any rights to sub-licence unless expressly stated otherwise. Each of the parties shall warrant that they have all the rights to use any Background IP during the term of the agreement and has the right to grant such licenses. Arrangements for use of jointly-owned IP and Foreground IP will also be set out in the Consortium Agreement. Outputs developed as a result of VITALISE will be openly available to the VITALISE audience and beyond to the maximum extent possible, except for the Ips transferred to the consortium partners interested in using them after project's lifecycle.

These valuable Results will be protected by their owner(s) through filing of patent application where possible, or other IP protection measures. The parties undertake not to leave valuable Results unprotected.

7.3 Transfer of results

Each partner may transfer ownership of its own results following the procedures of the GA (Article 30, Transfer and Licensing of Results). It may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its results, in Attachment 3 of the CA. Other partners hereby waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to a transfer to listed third parties according to the GA Article 30.1. The transferring partner shall, however, at the time of the transfer, inform other partners of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of other partners will not be affected by such transfer (for more, see Section 8 of the CA).

7.4 Dissemination of results

No dissemination of Results will take place before a decision is made regarding its possible protection. It is expected that the project will fill in at least one patent application (AUTH) for RAI certification number. The exploitation manager (WP13 leader) will make regular IP searches

throughout the project, in order to a) keep up-to-date with the IP landscape in the field b) assess the viability of their expected patent application.

Moreover, in order to maximise project knowledge, participants will prepare publications based on their work in the project. Steps will be taken to ensure open access to peer-reviewed publications in line with the requirements of Horizon 2020. The consortium will aim to work in line with the principles of the Open Research Data Pilot. The standard approach will be to follow the 'green' route to open access, i.e. copies of publications will be deposited before, alongside or after their publication. The consortium will have dedicated part of project's budget to cover the fees associated with open access publication to facilitate dissemination and reuse of the project's results. Project participants, for various reasons, may need to submit articles to journals (or proceedings) that only offer a lower level of open access, requiring either parallel publication or an embargo period.

The need for this will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis and will balance benefits against the less convenient or delayed access to the result. In any case, at least the final author's version of every accepted paper will be made publicly available, in accordance with the rules posed by many journals, e.g., for the case of IEEE publications. In this respect, the project will use widely self-archiving (or green open access) services for the research community such as ResearchGate (or Academia) that will allow balancing between traditional publications & open access. Dissemination leading partner VILABS (WP13), with the support of ENOLL and the rest partners will be responsible to track publications and the level of their compliance to open access, as part of dissemination task (T13.1). A record will be kept including all IP assets that the project creates and plans to create. This will be augmented by periodic discussions at the project's management board, reviewing the IP asset list and checking whether exploitation paths are explored for the most valuable IP. Also, for IPR protection, VITALISE will put in place a simple publication notification procedure, so that partners wishing to publish or otherwise disclose project activities and results can notify the other partners in good time. The publication notification and IP asset tracking procedures will be lightweight, requiring partners to fill in simple templates that will be shared via VITALISE's document management tool, considering the classification assigned to the planned deliverables according to the rules of general dissemination focus or restricted to the consortium.

7.5 Joint ownership

Two or more partners own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and if it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each partner, or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (under article 26 of the GA).

In this case, partners concerned must conclude to a joint ownership agreement (in writing). This agreement should cover:

- Specific conditions for granting licenses (if they are different from those already set out in the GA).
- Criteria or principles for 'fair and reasonable compensation' to be provided to the other joint owners, if a non – exclusive license is granted to a third party (if appropriate).
- How disputes will be settled (e.g., via a mediator, applicable law etc.) where no joint ownership agreement has yet been concluded.
- Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- The joint owners automatically have the right under the GA to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license) to exploit jointly (without prior authorisation from the other joint owners).
- The joint owner that intends to grant the license must give the other joint owners at least 45 calendar days advance notice (together with sufficient information, to check if the proposed compensation is fair and reasonable), as well as fair and reasonable compensation.

- Joint owners are free to agree on different arrangements in their joint-ownership agreement. Joint owners may abandon joint ownership only after the jointly-owned results have been produced.'

8 References

[1]	Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020, available online at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf
[2]	The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties, available online at: http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/about/logos/eu-emblem-rules-hr.pdf